

METHODS AND MEANS OF EXPRESSIVENESS

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Abstract: Uzbek language as well as all other languages a method that creates expressiveness-emotionality and have means. Language them by grouping events, generally "method" we called it. That is, we called expressive-emotionality in phonetic phenomena a phonetic method, and its expression in word forms a morphological method. Based on this principle, phonetic expression of expressive-emotional expression in Uzbek lexical, morphological and syntactic methods are defined.

Key words: facial expression, gestures, syntactic units, literary language, universal language, mimics, semantics, focus, modern text.

INTRODUCTION

In the current Uzbek language, there are the following forms of phonetic enhancement of meaning: 1) strong pronunciation of a vowel; 2) vowel lengthening (quantitative accent); 3) consonant layering (gemination). In the application of the listed phonetic phenomena there are specific terms and conditions. Also express phonetically there are some forms, and in addition to strengthening, weakening, it expresses meanings such as caressing.

MAIN PART

These meanings are sound changes, sound change and vowel lengthening, sound gain and dividing the word into syllables, pronouncing each syllable strongly is brought about by such methods. Expressiveness can define such phenomena as polysemanticism, trope, stylistically limited lexicon, synonymy and phraseology as expressive lexical-phraseological tools. The listed language phenomena are active and productive in creating expressiveness are tools. Polysemanticisms are neutral in one sense and neutral in another (figural - figurative meaning) serves to express an expressive-emotional thought.

Synonymy is the basis of stylistics and plays an important role in creating synonymous units and expressions occupies.

Phraseologisms are events, characters are people having a strong influence on the mind, fully expressing the result of this strong influence in speech, in general, is a language phenomenon created on the basis of the goal of achieving the effectiveness of thought.

The phenomenon of gradation in phraseologisms is especially important in terms of expressiveness allows to express at this level. For example, if the expression "to have hair on end" is considered the lowest level in terms of expressiveness, it is known using phonetic or grammatical means increases and creates a unique gradation. A language phenomenon with the possibility of gradation all the time to be able to express yourself will have. Because gradation itself is the power of meaning means to be graded in terms of.

The morphological method of expression of expressiveness-emotionality means the expression of expressiveness-emotionality by means of special word forms, as well as by special use of a form expressing a certain grammatical meaning.

Another way to express expressiveness is the analytical form of repetition of words. In the demonstrative form of monosyllabic words, using the exit agreement form, in the question-answer form, with repetition using the possessive form of the adjective, the strong sign level is expressed.

Expressiveness means increasing the impact of the expression of thought. Everything that makes the speech brighter, more impressive, more impressive is an expression. So, speech expressiveness is speech are bright, impressive, pictorial impression-making tools.

It was said above that the methods and means of expressing expressiveness are many and varied. When expressiveness is approached from the point of view of expression compared to other fields, the possibilities of syntax are enormous. Expressiveness is a syntactic method of expression both in communication and in subjective attitude can show its true nature. V.A. Bogoroditsky said, "Morphology is the definition of certain categories (word categories), they consist of inventories of forms. Syntax is the word forms it shows everything in action and life, in the composition of speech". It shows the interrelationship of morphology and syntax and the grammatical essence. If we assume that the sentence is made up of words and that the word has a real life in the sentence, manifests its true semantic essence, then the above we imagine the essence of the thought even more deeply. The possibility of syntax is not limited to this. Prosodic - intonation tools are also important in it. In other words, imagining syntactic events outside of intonation or vice versa can't be done. Speak because of intonation it will be possible to organize itself, assign its semantic and grammatical features. Most importantly, talk in creating neutral and expressive content and intonation is of particular importance in distinguishing them.

The possibilities of syntax in expressing expressiveness are therefore wide and rich, as is its object are sentences. "The importance of syntax for stylistics is determined

by the fact that, first of all, speech thinking and communication as the basic unit of speech serves for, and secondly, the sentence differs in that it has different forms in the Russian language". This opinion of A.N Gvozdev is not limited to stylistics, the expressiveness and emotionality of speech, it can also be applied to the facts of the Uzbek language.

Therefore, a copy of this movement is reflected by means of words ("head shakes"). So, gestures and facial expressions are actually non-linguistic phenomena, which can be used both outside of speech and as an auxiliary tool during speech. But it always happens as a result of the influence of an objective presence or interlocutor on the speaking mind. Therefore, it is expressed indirectly or indirectly related to language.

Gestures and facial expressions as auxiliary means of communication occur mainly in the process of oral speech. Expressiveness and emotionality can be expressed through different language tools in all forms of speech, and the same meanings can be expressed using gestures and facial expressions. For example, head movement (vertical or horizontal) expressing affirmation and negation in dialogic speech (without vocal speech) mainly indicates intellectual relations. For example, know negation if the pointing gesture is performed together with vocal speech, it can express an expressive reaction (in which the head is shaken and "no" is said with a special intonation). This action (gesture) is performed without sound, to the situation according to different, even exclamatory words can express different meanings. Examples: Our Eshon that's it... But there are two faults: He didn't give it out of hand, but by making friends with his wife while he was leaving, someone behind him hung his sword on Kifayat Khan he says. Eshon said, "It was a very sharp speech." in the sense of "shaking his head" he laughed hard (A. Qahhor).

As in lexical units, mimicry, especially in gesticulation, is omosemic, synosemic, antosemic, observation of the presence of monosemic, polysemic features. But here is their expressiveness in speech serving as an auxiliary tool for expression we want to be content with showing. Gesture and mimicry of the speaker to reality, conversation different psychophysiological relations to the dosh reflects.

Mimics, especially gestures, stand with their meaning to the birth of phraseologism as a result of sib is the basis: like his eyes popping out of their sockets, biting his finger. Gestures and facial expressions are real in the process of conversational speech if it is performed in a written speech, it is mainly in the author's sentence part of constructions with quotation sentences and the scene is explained in the remarks section of works.

It takes into account the social character, national character, and specific "semantics" of gestures and facial expressions. If so, this phenomenon deserves to be studied in detail it will be clear. Here, this matter (incident) was brought to the reader's attention only as a reference. expression, and conversely, the form of expression describes its content. The form and content of the sentence basket determines its function. Conformity of content and forms, usual use is communicative in function, and "unusual" uses appear in stylistic function. For example, it is usual for an affirmation form to represent the content of an affirmation. If he expresses a neutral attitude at the time, his negation its use in the content creates an expressive attitude.

There are two types of negative forms when they are used in a sentence the situation is observed:

1. The first negation in order negate the second negation (negate the negation), a strong affirmation follows.

2. The second negation to the first if not related, the content of the negation is preserved. The negation in the clause is general for the sentence, while the negation in the other clause is often specific in nature. Sentences with tight constructions are mainly artistic style is characteristic and often serves to express expressiveness. They are short, but concise, meaningful speech is characterized by the form.

Encouragement focuses on the idea to be expressed attracting the attention of a person (in the broadest sense), even him used for purposes such as advance warning. That's why there is a special emphasis on it. There are emotional feelings that come out. Therefore, motivation often makes the speech effective, it indicates the emotional attitude of the speaker to the listener. Expressiveness is the object of comparison when expressing and determining its level, and theirs What is the difference, distance, interval between the signs the longer, the greater the level of expressiveness.

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

Objects of the same gender, one type, to the object of comparison if taken, there will be no expressiveness. Different type, gender objects (for example, a person and an animal or bird) expressiveness is compared, and how much of it is different to be reflected depending on the conditions. If the comparison is realistic, the expressiveness is weak. Unreal character and in analogy (for example, comparing the human heart to a hot spring) expressiveness is strong.

The color of modernity of comparison is expressiveness serves to determine the level. For example, the phrase "like a burnt chicken" is quite old and is common in speech is applied. Accordingly, the level of expressiveness in it weakened. Syntactic synonymy in expressing expressiveness event also has a special place. Where there is

synonymy, there is an opportunity to select, sort and use the appropriate one. Where there is, there is gradation. Where there is gradation and there is expressiveness. The presence of synonymy among syntactic units, especially stylistics is considered a very valuable material for. Special stylistic figures (irony, cutting) to ensure the expressiveness of speech, rather, they are speech phenomena created on the basis of this goal.

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